

Recent and Upcoming Activities

Meet us at the following events:

ARM DDT debugger training for Earth System Modellers at BSC, 6 March 2018, Barcelona (ES)

EGU, 8-13 April 2018, Vienna (AT)

5° HPC ESIWACE/ENES Workshop, 17-18 May 2018, Lecce (IT)

6th European Seminar on Computing (ESCO), 3 - 8 June 2018, Pilsen (CZ)

Teratec Forum 2018, 19-20 June 2018, Campus Teratec, Bruyères-le-Châtel (FR)

ISC High Performance 2018, 24-28 June 2018, Frankfurt (DE)

Platform for Advanced Scientific Computing 2018 (PASC 2018), 2-4 July 2018, Basel (CH)

18th ECMWF Workshop on HPC in Meteorology, 24-28 September 2018

Supercomputing 2018, 11-16 November 2018, Dallas (USA)

More information on www.esiwace.eu/events

Initial cloud distribution for demonstrator using a very high resolution global atmosphere model.

At a glance

esiwace
CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE IN SIMULATION OF WEATHER
AND CLIMATE IN EUROPE

Title: Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe

Instrument: European research infrastructures (including e-Infrastructures) · work programme 2014-2015 · Call: EINFRA-5-2015 · Topic H2020-EINFRA-2015-1 (RIA), H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. · Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures

EC Contribution: 4.95 million €

Duration: 1 Sep 2015 – 31 Aug 2019

Consortium: 16 partners from seven countries

Project Coordinator: Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum (DKRZ), Germany

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 675191

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Project Objectives

ESIWACE substantially improves efficiency and productivity of numerical **weather** and **climate** simulation on **high-performance computing (HPC)** platforms by supporting the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modeling (ESM).

A special focus is the establishment of high-resolution global simulation demonstrators which will, once pushed towards production on exascale systems in future, open up entirely new research opportunities and perspectives.

Project Impacts

Weather and **climate** computing has always been among the key drivers for **HPC** development, with domain-specific scientific and technical requirements that stretch the capability and capacity of existing soft- and hardware to the limits.

Performing co-design at hard- and software level, ESIWACE directly interacts with and impacts on the industrial **HPC** eco-system and fosters collaboration of **weather** and **climate** science, **HPC** research and industry at the European scale.

High-Resolution Demonstrators

A key target is to reach global models with spatial resolutions that allow simulating convective clouds and small-scale ocean eddies. This will provide much more fidelity in the representation of high-impact regional events. Global cloud resolving models need spatial resolutions of at least 1 km. ESIWACE aims at enabling the implementation and operation of the infrastructures required to address the **HPC** challenges presented by this class of science cases.

Scalability of IFS- and ICON-based atmosphere-only global high-resolution demonstrators.

ESiWACE Themes

The **scalability** theme coordinates performance assessment and upgrade development of high-resolution **weather** and **climate** models, tools, coupling and I/O technologies to provide the simulation technology required at exascale.

The **usability** theme focuses on the ease-of-use of available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures for Earth system models on current peta-scale supercomputers.

The **exploitability** theme addresses major data handling barriers that pose severe bottlenecks in **HPC** for data-intensive ESM.

Governance and Engagement

ESiWACE follows a user-driven approach. A major aim is therefore to create and sustain a governance structure which ensures that the users from the **weather** and **climate** community inside and outside the ESIWACE consortium are actively involved in both

- the development of the high-resolution demonstrators, and
- the definition of scope and priorities of the ESIWACE agenda and related services.

ESiWACE therefore leverages two established European networks: the European Network for Earth system modeling (ENES) and the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF).

ENES: <https://verc.enes.org>

ECMWF: <http://www.ecmwf.int>

The Consortium

ESiWACE is coordinated by DRKZ and brings together 16 partners from seven countries having outstanding expertise in the fields of weather, climate and HPC.

Coordinator: **DKRZ**
DEUTSCHES KLIMARECHENZENTRUM

WEATHER **CLIMATE** **HPC**

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Wetter und Klima aus einer Hand Centre for Mediterranean and the Caribbean Climatic Now part of ARM

 National Centre for Atmospheric Science
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL **ICHEC**
Irish Centre for High-End Computing